

Electrophilic Iron Catalyst Paired with a Lithium Cation Enables Selective Functionalization of Non-Activated Aliphatic C-H Bonds via Metallocarbene Intermediates

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Abstract: Combining an electrophilic iron complex $[\text{Fe}^{\text{F}}\text{pda}](\text{THF})_2$ (3) [$\text{F}^{\text{pda}} = \text{N},\text{N}'\text{-bis}(\text{pentafluorophenyl})\text{-}o\text{-phenylenediamide}$] with the pre-activation of α -alkyl-substituted α -diazoesters reagents by $\text{LiAl}(\text{OR}^{\text{F}})_4$ [$\text{OR}^{\text{F}} = (\text{OC}(\text{CF}_3)_3)$] provides unprecedented access to selective iron-catalyzed intramolecular functionalization of strong alkyl $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-H}$ bonds. Reactions occur at 25 °C via α -alkyl-metallocarbene intermediates, and with activity/selectivity levels similar to those of rhodium carboxylate catalysts. Mechanistic investigations reveal a crucial role of the lithium cation in the rate-determining formation of the electrophilic iron-carbene intermediate, which then proceeds by concerted insertion into the C-H bond.

Introduction

Carbon-carbon $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-C}(\text{sp}^3)$ bond-formation methodologies are fundamental in many synthetic transformations. Among the different existing strategies,^[1] the formal metal-mediated insertion of carbene fragments into $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-H}$ bonds^[2] is an appealing methodology because of its greater atom economy when compared with the most extended cross-coupling procedures, employing organometallic coupling partners (boron, zinc, or Grignard reagents).^[1a,b] Despite the robustness of $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-H}$ bonds,^[3] making difficult their chemical manipulation, a variety of transition-metal carbene species (copper, cobalt, silver, palladium, rhodium, and ruthenium), generated from diazo reagents, are capable of catalyzing these insertion reactions.^[4] In contrast, iron systems, which are attractive from a sustainability perspective,^[5] have shown modest activity and are limited to less demanding processes, including cyclopropanation reactions,^[6] and alkylation of $\text{C}(\text{sp}^2)\text{-H}$,^[7] heteroatom-hydrogen,^[8] and relatively weak allylic and benzylic ($\text{BDE} < 90 \text{ Kcalmol}^{-1}$) $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-H}$ bonds (Scheme 1).^[9] Pioneering studies by the group of Che^[10] proved the feasibility of iron(III) porphyrins to effect this

methodology by stoichiometric functionalization of cyclohexene, cumene, and tetrahydrofuran, using diphenyldiazomethane as the carbene precursor at high temperatures (60°C–80°C; Scheme 1 a).

Updating this strategy to a catalytic version, the group of Woo^[11] reported intermolecular insertion of carbene fragments, generated from methyl phenyldiazoacetate, into the *Scheme 1*. State of art of iron-carbene-mediated $\text{C}(\text{sp}^3)\text{-H}$ functionalization.

Previous work

C-H bonds of cyclohexane and tetrahydrofuran, mediated by an iron(III) porphyrin catalyst at 80°C (Scheme 1 b). Although this study opened new ground for iron chemistry, it was later reported that these diazoester compounds undergo formal carbene insertion in the absence of iron, although in lower yields.^[12] More recently, intramolecular alkylation of weak allylic and benzylic C(sp³)-H bonds has been reported using heme-like iron(III) phthalocyanine catalysts, and intermolecular enantioselective alkylation of activated C(sp³)-H bonds (BDE C-H > 90 Kcalmol⁻¹) is well established.^[3] We hypothesized that replacing the porphyrin (or related) by ligands of highly electrophilic character would lead to the formation of electron-poor iron-carbene species by reaction with diazo compounds, thus overcoming energetically demanding C-H alkylation processes under mild reaction conditions.

This scenario contrasts to the one operating for the isoelectronic iron oxos^[13] and iron nitrenes^[14] in which, upon ligand design, functionalization of less reactive C(sp³)-H bonds (BDE C-H > 90 Kcalmol⁻¹) is well established.^[3] We hypothesized that replacing the porphyrin (or related) by ligands of highly electrophilic character would lead to the formation of electron-poor iron-carbene species by reaction with diazo compounds, thus overcoming energetically demanding C-H alkylation processes under mild reaction conditions.

In our aim to develop iron-carbene species with the ability to functionalize strong C(sp³)-H bonds, herein we report an electrophilic iron complex, [Fe(^Fpda)(THF)]₂ (3) [^Fpda = *N,N'*-bis(pentafluorophenyl)-*o*-phenylenediamide], which is arranged in a unique dimeric fashion within *ortho*-phenylenediamide iron chemistry, chemistry traditionally dominated by formation of the more stable [FeL₂] fragment as described by the group of Wieghardt.^[15] For comparison reasons, the related complex [Fe(^{Mes}pda)(Tol)] (4) [^{Mes}pda = *N,N'*-bis(2,4,6-trimethylphenyl)-*o*-phenylenediamine], displaying a poorer electrophilic nature, has been also investigated. Effectively, we disclose unprecedented iron-catalyzed intramolecular carbene insertion into a variety of non-activated aliphatic C-H bonds, via iron-carbene intermediates (Scheme 1 e), under mild reaction conditions (25°C). The reaction is critically based on two novel aspects: a) pre-activation of the diazoester reagent by the Lewis acid LiAl(OR^F)₄ [OR^F = (OC(CF₃)₃)], which enables formation of the iron-carbene species under mild reaction conditions, and b) the electrophilic character of 3, which permits functionalization of non-activated aliphatic C-H bonds. Remarkably 3 exhibits activity and selectivity levels comparable to rhodium carboxylate catalysts.

Results and Discussion

The *ortho*-phenylenediamine ligands 1 and 2 (see Scheme 2) were synthesized by nucleophilic aromatic substitution between lithium 1,2-phenylenediamide and hexafluorobenzene for compound 1, and Buchwald-Hartwig amination of 1,2-dibromobenzene with 2,4,6-trimethylaniline in the case of 2, according to previous reports in the literature.^[16]

Metallation of 1 with the bisamide iron compound {Fe[N(SiMe₃)₂]₂(THF)} in a mixture THF/hexane (1:9) at room temperature led to the formation of [Fe(^Fpda)(THF)]₂

Scheme 2. Syntheses of 3 and 4.

(3), as a pale orange solid in 82 % yield (Scheme 2). Similarly, reaction of 2 and {Fe[N(SiMe₃)₂]₂(THF)} using toluene as a solvent resulted in isolation of a dark purple solid identified as compound [Fe(^{Mes}pda)(Tol)] (4; 75 % yield; Scheme 2). Single-crystal X-ray analysis of 3 (Figure 1a and Table 1)

Figure 1. Molecular structures of a) 3 and b) 4 with thermal ellipsoids at 50 % probability. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

reveals a dimeric structure formed by two units of [Fe(^Fpda)-(THF)] and a central {Fe₂N₂} core, where the iron centers are connected by two bridging nitrogen atoms of two ^Fpda ligands. Fulfilling their coordination sphere the metallic centers are terminally coordinated by the second nitrogen atom of the *N,N'*-bidentate ligand, and by a molecule of THF. Inspection of the monomeric asymmetric unit [Fe(^Fpda)-(THF)] reveals two significantly different Fe-N bond distances, Fe1-N1 2.112 (1) and Fe1-N2 1.969 (1), attributed to the bridging character of N1 between Fe1 and Fe1', while N2 coordinates terminally to Fe1. Similarly, within the {Fe₂N₂} core two different Fe-N bond distances are observed, with the previous Fe1-N1 bond distance longer than the one formed between the same N1 and the neighboring iron atom Fe1'-N1 2.069(1). These Fe-N bond distances are within the range of high-spin Fe^{II} compounds supported by bidentate ligands (Fe-N > 2.0 Å).^[17] In contrast, 4 (Figure 1b and

Table 1: Selected bond distances of 3 and 4.

Bond distances	3	4
Fe1-O1	2.017(1)	–
Fe1-N1	2.112(1)	1.881(2)
Fe1-N'1	2.069(1)	–
Fe1-N2	1.969(1)	1.867(2)
Fe-G _{Tol average}	–	2.09(1)
N1-C1	1.446(2)	1.359(4)
N2-C2	1.399(2)	1.359(4)
C1-C2	1.411(2)	1.426(4)
C1-C6	1.390(3)	1.410(4)
C2-C3	1.399(3)	1.414(4)
C3-C4	1.388(3)	1.375(4)
C4-C5	1.380(3)	1.407(4)
C5-C6	1.392(3)	1.382(4)

Table 1) exhibits a monomeric h^6 -toluene adduct with Mes_2pda acting as a terminal $\text{N,N}'$ -bidentate ligand and with shorter Fe-N bonds (average 1.87(1) c).

The different nature of the formed complexes with the non-nitrogen donor ligands, THF adduct in 3 and toluene ρ adduct in 4, points to different electronic configurations of each iron complex because of the redox-active nature of the $\text{N,N}'$ -bidentate ligands employed. The latter is confirmed by comparison of the metrical data of the ligand backbones of 3 and 4, following Wieghardt's structural approach to determine the redox form of the ligand and metal in complexes supported by *ortho*-phenylene diamine ligands.^[15] Thus 3 displays an aromatic phenylene ring (C-C_{average} 1.39(1) c) and single C-N bonds (C-N_{average} 1.42(2) c), whereas species 4 exhibits subtle dearomatization on the phenylene ring with two sets of C-C bonds (average C_a-C_a and C_a-C_b 1.417(8) c; C_b-C_g average 1.378(5) c), as well as shorter C-N bond distances (C-N_{average} 1.359(4) c). These data are consistent with a dianionic *ortho*-phenylenediamide bidentate ligand binding an Fe²⁺ metallic center in 3, similar to the homoleptic [Fe(^Fpda)₂][AsPh₄] previously reported by Wieghardt, although in this case two ^Fpda²⁻ units coordinate the same metallic center.^[15b] The isolation of 3 relies on the use of the iron base {Fe[N(SiMe₃)₂]₂(THF)}, which precludes the presence of an excess of dianionic diamide ligand, as when the lithiated diamide is used as a transmetallating reagent and

ultimately avoids formation of the [FeL₂] fragment.

In contrast, 4 is better described as an iron(I) *ortho*-diiminosemi-quinonate with metrical data similar to the [Fe(^Fpda)(Tol)] compound reported by Song.^[18] In agreement with the electronic structures suggested by X-ray crystallography, ¹H NMR characterization in C₆D₆ solution Fe^I (d⁷) metallic center with the unpaired electron on the *ortho*-diiminosemiquinonate ligand, as it was reported for the isostructural [Fe(^Fpda)(Tol)].^[18] In contrast, in C₆D₆ 3 displays a paramagnetic behavior showing two resonances at $\delta = 25$ and 15 ppm, accounting for the four aromatic protons at the backbone of the bisamide ligand, and a solution magnetic moment $m_{\text{eff}} = 4.71(3) m_B$ per dimer at room temperature. Confirming retention of the solid-state structure of 3 in C₆D₆ solution, when its ¹H NMR spectrum was registered in [D₈]THF, a shift of the latter signals, assigned to the dimer ($\delta = 25$ and 15 ppm), was observed towards higher field ($\delta = -18$ and -22 ppm), in agreement with THF coordination to the iron centers and breaking up of the dimer to generate a monomer species. Thus, the deduced spin-only value for 3 in C₆D₆ is lower than that expected for two uncoupled high-spin iron(II) (6.9 m_B), and can be attributed to antiferromagnetic coupling between the two vicinal iron atoms (2.615(1) c) of the dimer.

To begin our investigations on C-H alkylation, we tested the catalytic activities of 3 (2.5 mol%) and 4 (5 mol%) in the intramolecular C-H alkylation of the diazoester 5 in CH₂Cl₂ at 25 °C for 24 hours (Table 2, entries 1 and 2). The reactions provided poor conversions (7–8 %) of 5 into the desired product 5a, where intramolecular alkylation has taken place at the benzylic position, and the *a,b*-unsaturated ester side-product 5b, generated in a *b*-hydride migration process, or alternatively by two consecutive hydrogen atom abstraction (HAT) steps, as it has been recently reported by the group of De Bruin for intramolecular C-H alkylation catalysis via radical cobalt-carbene intermediates.^[19]

Table 2: Optimization for catalytic functionalization of 5.^[a]

Entry	Catalyst	Cocatalyst (%)	Yield		
			5	5a (<i>anti/syn</i>)	5b (<i>E/Z</i>)
1	3 (2.5)	–	92%	2% (75:25)	3% (47:53)
2	4 (5)	–	93%	5% (45:55)	–
3	3 (2.5)	LiAl(OR ^F) ₄ (5)	52%	31% (87:13)	12% (32:68)
4	4 (5)	LiAl(OR ^F) ₄ (5)	82%	7% (89:11)	8% (35:65)
5	3 (2.5)	LiAl(OR ^F) ₄ (15)	42%	40% (86:14)	15% (27:73)
6	3 (2.5)	LiAl(OR ^F) ₄ (25)	4%	60% (76:24)	35% (19:81)
7	3 (2.5)	LiAl(OR ^F) ₄ (50)	–	51% (84:16)	48% (42:58)
8	3 (2.5)	LiAl(OR ^F) ₄ (75)	–	48% (78:22)	48% (47:53)
9	3 (2.5)	LiAl(OR ^F) ₄ (100)	–	45% (83:17)	50% (46:54)
10	–	LiAl(OR ^F) ₄ (25)	> 99%	–	–
11	3 (2.5)	NaBAR ^F (25)	89%	7% (85:15)	–
12	[Fe(OTf) ₂ (PyTACN)] (5)	LiAl(OR ^F) ₄ (25)	> 99%	–	–
13	[Rh(OAc) ₂] ₂ (2.5)	–	–	68% (93:7)	31% (1:99)
14	TpBr ₃ Cu(NCMe) (5)	–	–	6% (> 99:1)	92% (37:63)

[a] Reaction conditions: [5] = 0.08 mm. Yields of 5a, 5b, and diastereomeric ratios were determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy using dibromomethane as an internal standard.

Despite this lack of reactivity, during the addition of 5 to the CH₂Cl₂ solution of 3 we observed an immediate color change from orange to dark brown. Analysis of the mixture resulting from the reaction of stoichiometric amounts of 5 and 3 by infrared spectroscopy shows a band shift to a lower value ($Du = 13 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) for the C=O functional group (Figures 2 a–c),

Figure 2. Expanded IR spectra displaying C=O and N₂ bands of a) 5, b) the reaction mixture of 5 and 3 (1:0.5), c) the reaction mixture of 5 and 3 (1:1), d) the reaction mixture of 5 and LiAl(OR^F)₄ (1:0.05), e) the reaction mixture of 5 and LiAl(OR^F)₄ (1:0.15), and f) the reaction mixture of 5 and LiAl(OR^F)₄ (1:0.25). * band belonging to 3. For full spectra see the Supporting Information.

while the band assigned to the N=N functional group is modified to a more modest extent ($Du = -8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). These observations suggest that the iron compound is unable to effect formation of the metalcarbene intermediate upon nitrogen release of the diazo compound, and instead a novel adduct species through the binding of the O donor atom of the carbonyl group [Fe-O(C)], present in the diazo reagent, to the Lewis acid Fe^{II} of 3 is formed. This scenario is reminiscent to the one recently reported for the C(sp²)-H bond alkylation reactions via non-heme iron-carbene species. In this case, computational studies rationalize the high reaction temperatures (808C) required for dissociation of an unproductive Fe-O(C) adduct formed between the iron catalyst and the oxygen atom of the carbonyl group of ethyl diazoacetate.^[7a]

We hypothesized that the undesired Fe-O(C) interaction can be disfavored by addition of a stronger Lewis acid than the iron centers present in 3 and 4. Indeed, by repeating the infrared spectroscopy of the mixture formed by 5 and variable amounts of the lithium salt LiAl(OR^F)₄ [OR^F = (OC(CF₃)₃) (5–25 mol%)], we observed a split in two of the investigated C=O bands assigned to free 5 (1690 cm⁻¹) and lithium-bound 5 (1654 cm⁻¹; Figures 2 d–f). According to this assignment, the intensity of the free diazo band systematically decreased to depletion in favor of the adduct band as the concentration range of LiAl(OR^F)₄ increased from 5 to 25 mol%. Beyond a 25 mol% concentration of lithium aluminate, no changes were observed in the IR spectra. Of relevance to these

observations, this coordination mode reproduces the one observed for the interaction of lactones with lithium inorganic salts, which occurs through the carbonyl group.^[20] In parallel, within the range of LiAl(OR^F)₄ concentrations studied, the

N=N stretching frequency experiences a 15 cm⁻¹ shift to higher energies, which can be rationalized by an additional,

but weaker, interaction between a lithium cation and 5 through the negatively polarized carbon center bearing the diazo fragment Li-C(N₂). In solution, a dynamic binding of lithium to 5 can be deduced by ¹H NMR study of the previously described reaction mixtures within the concentration range 5–25 mol% of LiAl(OR^F)₄, which display only one set of broad signals of the diazoester reagent (see Figures S127–S128 in the Supporting Information). Further evidence for the strong binding of 5 to lithium is provided by mass spectroscopy analysis of a reaction mixture of 5 and LiAl(OR^F)₄ (1:0.25), which exhibits peaks at $m/z = 471.2585$ and 239.1384 , corresponding to a mono- and bis-adduct between 5 and the lithium cation (see Figures S129–S131). Collectively, the data suggests the formation of a strong adduct between 5 and lithium, through the carbonyl group, which may be used to liberate the iron center, setting it up for carbene formation.

In agreement with the above described analysis, repeating the intramolecular C-H alkylation reaction of 5 catalyzed by 2.5 mol% of 3 and 5 mol% of 4, but now in presence of 5 mol% of LiAl(OR^F)₄ [OR^F = (OC(CF₃)₃)], resulted in enhanced conversions of 5 at 258C (Table 2, entries 3 and 4), with 3 having the highest reactivity and selectivity with a 48 % conversion and a 72:28 ratio (5 a/5 b), whereas 4 only rendered a 18 % conversion with a 47:53 ratio (5 a/5 b). Seeking to increase the yield of 5 a, we optimized the loading of the lithium salt LiAl(OR^F)₄ (entries 5–9), resulting in nearly quantitative conversion of 5, with the best 5 a/5b ratio and a high 5a diastereomeric ratio (76/24, *syn:anti*) at 25 mol% concentration (entry 6). Notably, this lithium concentration actually matches the absence of free diazo compound observed by infrared studies. Proof of the synergistic partnership between Fe and Li is found when the lithium aluminate LiAl(OR^F)₄ is reacted with 5 at 25 8C in the absence of 3, resulting in neither 5a nor 5b being observed (entry 10). Under the optimized reaction conditions we investigated the influence of each component in the catalytic reaction. Other alkali metal salts, such as NaBAR^F, have been used in more facile C(sp³)-H insertion reactions via iron-carbene species, playing the role as trapping reagents of the halogen atoms connected to the iron center, and generating a cationic and hence more reactive iron species.^[7,9b] In our case replacing LiAl(OR^F)₄ by NaBAR^F (entry 11) led to lower reactivity with only 7 % yield of 5 a, proving sodium to be a less affective cocatalyst, which is in agreement with the softer nature as a Lewis acid compared to the lithium cation.

To highlight the importance of low-coordinate iron centers to develop these C-H insertion reactions, replacement of 3 with an iron complex supported by a polydentate amino-based ligand, [Fe(OTf)₂(PyTACN)] (PyTACN = 1-(2-pyridylmethyl)-4,7-dimethyl-1,4,7-triazacyclononane; Table 2, entry 12),^[7] led to no formation of 5a with only the starting material 5 being recovered. This catalyst was recently shown to activate ethyl diazoacetate to effect chemoselective arene alkylation of alkyl arenes by a formal carbene insertion reaction: Reactions require 80 8C to proceed and did not display sp³ alkylation, even in the presence of weak tertiary C-H bonds. In addition, and for comparison reasons the studied cyclization was also subjected to rhodium catalysis.^[19]

Using 2.5 mol% of $[\text{Rh}(\text{OAc})_2]_2$ provided similar results to our iron-lithium catalytic system (entry 13). Drawing a comparison to iron catalysis in terms of sustainability, the earth-abundant copper metal supported by trispyrazolylborates have emerged as powerful catalysts for functionalizing unreactive hydrocarbons,^[21] however alkylation of **5** using the electron-deficient $\text{Tp}^{\text{Br}_3}\text{Cu}(\text{NCMe})$ ($\text{Tp}^{\text{Br}_3} = (\text{hydrottris}(3,4,5\text{-tribromo})\text{pyrazolyl})\text{borate}$) species led almost exclusively to the undesired **5b** (entry 14).

With the optimized reaction conditions in hand, we next investigated the viability of this catalytic Fe/Li system in intramolecular C-H alkylation of diazo substrates with varying degrees of electrophilicity (6–8, Table 3) and bonds of different strengths (9–19). Modification of the electronic properties of the diazo reagent resulted in no reaction in the case of the acceptor/acceptor substrate **6**, and in low

conversion of the donor/acceptor compound **7** towards a mixture of unidentified compounds. In addition, we also explored other carbene sources such as the *N*-tosylhydrazone **8**, which gives rise to the corresponding diazo reagent in situ upon deprotonation using a base (LiO^tBu), as it has been successfully used in cobalt catalysis.^[4d–g] However this methodology proved to be incompatible with the developed Fe/Li system.

The study was extended to donor/acceptor diazo reagents structurally similar to **5**, and containing benzylic C-H bonds. Using the electron-rich *para*-methoxy aryl diazoester reagent **9** led to the corresponding cyclopentane product **9a** in a high yield of 70 % upon isolation, while the electron-poor *para*-chloro-substituted compound **10** was transformed into **10a** in a diminished 39 % yield upon isolation (Table 3). Both **9a** and **10a** are formed in similar and modest diastereomeric ratio (d.r.) 77:23. Again, the differences observed in the yields agree with involvement of an electrophilic iron-carbene species as the active species, with enhanced reactivity as the nucleophilicity of the reactive C-H bond increases. Notably, directed by the formation of a favorable five-membered ring a strong alkyl C-H bond is functionalized over the weaker benzylic C-H bond, forming the five-membered ring **11a**, albeit in a modest 30% yield. These catalytic C-H alkylation reactions compared well with the only previous report in the literature for the catalytic intramolecular functionalization of benzylic C-H bonds via iron-carbene intermediates, as the latter required heating (458C) and higher catalyst loading (10 mol%) to carry out these reactions under similar reaction times and yields.^[9b] In addition, these results (**5a**, **9a–11a**) suggest that formation of olefin side products is substrate-dependent, making this reaction more competent as the functionalization of the desired C-H bond is less favorable, as observed for **10** and **11** in which the *a,b*-unsaturated ester product is generated in higher yields. Of relevance, reactions exhibit an excellent mass balance. For each substrate, the sum of yields of alkylated product and the *a,b*-unsaturated ester account for the total amount of initial substrate. Encouraged by the formation of **11a** under mild reaction conditions, we next explored functionalization of strong C-H bonds found in alkyl derivatives. Starting with a less demanding one, **3** in combination with $\text{LiAl}(\text{OR}^F)_4$ was able to produce cyclization upon functionalization of a tertiary C-H bond present in diazoester reagent **12**, generating **12a** in 56% yield. A similar yield (64%) was obtained for the cyclopentane derivative **13a**, when substrate **13**, containing a more challenging secondary C-H bond, was subjected to the catalytic Fe/Li system. As was observed for benzylic C-H bonds, formation of a five-membered ring predominates over the possibility of forming larger size rings as in the case of the diazoester **14**, which renders **14a** in 60 % yield. More importantly, formation of cyclopentane derivatives (**11a–14a**) occurs in an excellent diastereomeric ratio (*anti:syn* +95:5). Beyond monocyclic products, the developed methodology gives access to bicyclic spiro-compounds (**15a**, **16a**) and fused ring products (**17a**, **18a**) in moderate to good yields (47–70%). Contrastingly, **3** in combination with the lithium salt activates the most challenging primary C-H bonds present in **19** in nearly stoichiometric yield (6%).

Table 3: Substrate scope.^[a]

[a] Reaction conditions: $[\text{5–19}] = 0.08$ mm. Conversions of **6–8** were determined by ^1H NMR spectroscopy using dibromomethane as an internal standard. Yields of **5a**, **9a–19a** and **5b**, **9b–19b**, were determined by ^1H NMR spectroscopy using dibromomethane as an internal standard. Diastereomeric ratios were determined by GC and ^1H NMR spectroscopy. The *anti* diastereomer for **5a**, **9a–19a** was determined to be the major isomer by NMR characterization. Yields for products isolated from 1 mmol scale reactions are reported within square brackets and their corresponding diastereomeric ratios determined by GC and ^1H NMR spectroscopy. rsm=recovered starting material. [b] Unidentified products. [c] d.r. (63:25:12), d.r. for isolated product (68:29:3) determined by GC and ^1H NMR spectroscopy. Relative stereochemistry was not determined. [d] d.r. (94:6) determined by GC, relative stereochemistry was not determined.

We envisioned these reactions proceeding by a concerted alkylation process (Figure 3 a), in which the iron-carbene species is formed by nitrogen extrusion from the corresponding lithium-diazoester adduct with subsequent insertion into the C-H bond, forming a new C-C and C-H bond simultaneously, releasing the organic product and regenerating the active catalyst. Nevertheless, two alternative scenarios can be proposed, such as formation of free carbene species to effect the observed C-H insertion reactions or a hydrogen-atom transfer initiated radical stepwise process, as in the case of iron-mediated C-H oxidation,^[13] amination,^[14] and a recently

described iron-phthalocyanine-catalyzed alkylation.^[9b] To distinguish between these three possibilities, we subjected our system to a variety of mechanistic analyses. First, generation of a free carbene was thermally (808C) achieved, and resulted in exclusive formation of the undesired 5b in a 48 % yield (Figure 3 b). Under the same reaction conditions (808C and absence of iron catalyst), addition of the Lewis acid LiAl(OR^F)₄ exclusively afforded 5b in quantitative yield (Figure 3 b). This acceleration is in agreement with the observed Li-C(N₂) interaction by IR spectroscopy, and at high temperatures favors formation of a free carbene. The lack of formation of 5a in the absence of 3 provides strong support for the necessary formation of an iron-carbene intermediate as the active species responsible for the C-H alkylation reactions.

Next, to shed light on the nature of the C-H activation step, the intramolecular kinetic isotope effect (KIE) was explored by alkylation of the partially deuterated diazoester reagent [D₁]-5. This experiment revealed two different values for each diastereomer, with the isotopic effect being lower, in the case of the major *anti* isomer [KIE = 2.3 (1)], than the one observed for the *syn* isomer [KIE = 4.3 (1); Figure 3 c]. For comparison reasons [D₁]-5 was also subjected to catalytic alkylation using the dimeric [Rh(OAc)₂]₂ catalysts, well-known to operate through C-H insertion,^[22] and afforded again two KIE values, 2.3 (1) for the *anti* isomer and 3.7 (1) for the *syn* isomer (Figure 3 c). The similar KIE values for both catalysts support the proposed concerted mechanism. In addition, the different results for each diastereomer in both metal-mediated reactions reflect two different transition states for the concerted insertion, as it has been also observed in previous rhodium-mediated carbene insertion reactions.^[23] To confirm the absence of radical intermediates, the radical trap TEMPO was added to the optimized alkylation reaction of 5. However, this experiment led to full recovery of the starting material (Figure 3 d). This result can be reasoned by preliminary reaction between 3 and TEMPO, rendering a species unable to form an iron-carbene active species. We next explored cyclization of the radical-clock substrate 20, which leads to the cyclopentane 20a in 72 % yield, with the cyclopropyl fragment intact (Figure 3 e). Hydride shift the product 20b accounts for the rest of the starting material. The lack of rearranged products is consistent with an insertion reaction, devoid of long lived radical or carbocationic intermediates.

Once the concerted mechanism was established, we explored the nature of the rate-determining step by kinetic

studies. Monitoring the C-H alkylation of 5 by ¹H NMR spectroscopy under the optimized reaction conditions (2.5 mol% of 3 and 25 mol% of LiAl(OR^F)₄) reveals a first-order dependence on the diazoester reagent (Figure S135). In addition, a KIE value of 1 was determined by product analysis of the competitive reaction between equimolar amounts of 5 and [D₁]-5 at low substrate conversion (15 %; Figure 3 c). Finally, variable-time normalization analysis^[24] for the intramolecular insertion reaction at 5, at different concentrations of LiAl(OR^F)₄ (25–40 mol%) revealed a fractional 1.5 order (see Figure S136), suggesting participation of more than one lithium cation through a coordination-dissociation equilibri-

Figure 3. a) Proposed mechanism of reaction. b) Generation of free carbene by thermal decomposition. c) KIE studies. d) C-H alkylation reaction in presence of TEMPO as a radical trap. e) C-H alkylation using radical probe 20.

um process. This data agrees with the IR studies, which show that 5 interacts with lithium through the carbonyl group, Li–O(C), and the negatively polarized carbon center, Li–C(N₂), requiring the latter to be replaced by iron for the formation of the iron-carbene species. Overall, these data are consistent with rate-limiting formation of the iron-carbene species, preceded by competition between a second lithium cation and iron for the C(N₂) center in an equilibrium process, which shifts towards the interaction with iron because of the irreversible formation of the iron-carbene species.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we describe an electrophilic iron complex (3), which in combination with LiAl(OR^F)₄ as a cocatalyst activates diazoesters under mild reaction conditions, resulting in intramolecular C(sp³)-H alkylation of a variety of benzyl and alkyl C-H bonds, ultimately leading to a variety of carbocyclic cyclopentanes as well as bicyclic spiro and fused ring compounds. High stereoselectivity is observed in the alkylation of the strong aliphatic sites. Mechanistic studies strongly suggest that the reactions proceed via highly reactive iron-carbene active species. Key to its formation is the binding of the carbonyl group of the diazoester reagent to lithium Li–O(C). Presumably this reaction blocks formation of unproductive Fe–O(C) species, favoring interaction of the diazo moiety with the iron center by replacement of the second lithium cation interacting with the diazo reagent via Li–C(N). This interaction then triggers release of nitrogen and formation of the reactive iron-carbene species in the rate-determining step. In addition, these studies show close similarities to rhodium-based carbene-transfer reactions which entail a concerted metallocarbene insertion into the C-H bond, forming the new C-C and C-H bonds, suggesting that the current iron-based system also operates by a C-H insertion process. Most relevant, the current systems extend the substrate scope of iron-carbene species towards site-selective alkylation of strong aliphatic C-H bonds, leading to transformations that so far have only been accessible with precious metals. Key to this finding is the tuning of the ligand architecture to endorse the iron center with a highly electrophilic character. Considering the structural versatility of this class of ligands, and the high level of diastereoselectivity observed in the functionalization of aliphatic sites, the development of catalyst-dependent site-selective and enantioselective transformations, akin to those established for rhodium carbenes, is envisioned.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords: C-H activation · carbenes · iron · lithium · reaction mechanisms

References

- [1] For comprehensive reviews in C(sp³)-C(sp³) methodologies, see: a) N. Kambe, T. Iwasakia, J. Terao, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2011, *40*, 4937–4947; b) R. Jana, T. P. Pathak, M. S. Sigman, *Chem. Rev.* 2011, *111*, 1417–1492; c) Z. Dong, Z. Ren, S. J. Thompson, Y. Xu, G. Dong, *Chem. Rev.* 2017, *117*, 9333–9403.
- [2] a) M. M. D&az-Requejo, A. Caballero, M. R. Fructos, P. J. P&rez, *Alkane C-H Activation by Single-Site Metal Catalysis*, Springer, Amsterdam, 2012, chap. 6; b) A. Caballero, M. M. Diaz-Requejo, M. R. Fructos, A. Olmos, J. Urbano, P. J. Perez, *Dalton Trans.* 2015, *44*, 20295–20307; c) A. Caballero, P. J. Perez, *Chem. Eur. J.* 2017, *23*, 14389–14393; d) A. Ford, H. Miel, A. Ring, C. N. Slaterry, A. R. Maguire, M. A. McKerverey, *Chem. Rev.* 2015, *115*, 9981–10080; e) H. Lu, P. Zhang, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2011, *40*, 1899–1909; f) M. P. Doyle, R. Duffy, M. Ratnikov, L. Zhou, *Chem. Rev.* 2010, *110*, 704–724.
- [3] Y.-R. Luo, *Comprehensive Handbook of Chemical Bond Energies*, CRC, Boca Raton, FL, 2007.
- [4] See Reference [2], and for recent examples, see: a) A. E. Shiely, L.-A. Clarke, C. J. Flynn, A. M. Buckley, A. Ford, S. E. Lawrence, A. R. Maguire, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* 2018, 2277–2289; b) Y. Wang, X. Wen, X. Cui, X. P. Zhang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2018, *140*, 4792–4796; c) X. Cui, X. Xu, L.-M. Jin, L. Wojtas, X. P. Zhang, *Chem. Sci.* 2015, *6*, 1219–1224; d) C. te Grotenhuis, B. G. Das, P. F. Kuijpers, W. Hageman, M. Trouwborst, B. de Bruin, *Chem. Sci.* 2017, *8*, 8221–8230; e) C. te Grotenhuis, N. van den Heuvel, J. I. van der Vlugt, B. De Bruin, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 2018, *57*, 140–145; *Angew. Chem.* 2018, *130*, 146–151; f) A. S. Karns, M. Goswami, B. de Bruin, *Chem. Eur. J.* 2018, *24*, 5253–5258; g) X. Wen, Y. Wang, X. P. Zhang, *Chem. Sci.* 2018, *9*, 5082–5086; h) A. Guti&rrrez Bonet, F. Julia-Hernandez, B. de Luis, R. Martin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2016, *138*, 6384–6387; i) A. R. Reddy, C. Y. Zhou, Z. Guo, J. H. Wei, C. M. Che, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 2014, *53*, 14175–14180; *Angew. Chem.* 2014, *126*, 14399–14404.
- [5] a) A. Fgrstner, *ACS Cent. Sci.* 2016, *2*, 778–789; b) S. Enthaler, K. Junge, M. Beller, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 2008, *47*, 3317–3321; *Angew. Chem.* 2008, *120*, 3363–3367; c) I. Bauer, H. J. Knolker, *Chem. Rev.* 2015, *115*, 3170–3387.
- [6] a) P. S. Coelho, E. M. Brustad, A. Kannan, F. H. Arnold, *Science* 2013, *339*, 307–310; b) J.-J. Shen, S.-F. Zhu, Y. Cai, H. Xu, X.-L. Xie, Q.-L. Zhou, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 2014, *53*, 13188–13191; *Angew. Chem.* 2014, *126*, 13404–13407.
- [7] a) V. Postils, M. Rodr&guez, G. Sabenya, A. Conde, M. M. D&az-Requejo, P. J. Perez, M. Costas, M. Sola, J. M. Luis, *ACS Catal.* 2018, *8*, 4313–4322; b) A. Conde, G. Sabenya, M. Rodr&guez, V. Postils, J. M. Luis, M. M. D&az-Requejo, M. Costas, J. P. P&rez,

- Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 2016, 55, 6530–6534; *Angew. Chem.* 2016, 128, 6640–6644.
- [8] a) G. Sreenilayama, R. Fasan, *Chem. Commun.* 2015, 51, 1532–1534; b) L. K. Baumann, H. M. Mbuvi, G. Du, L. K. Woo, *Organometallics* 2007, 26, 3995–4002; c) E. H. Wang, Y.-J. Ping, Z.-R. Li, H. Qin, Z.-J. Xu, C.-M. Che, *Org. Lett.* 2018, 20, 4641–4644.
- [9] a) R. K. Zhang, K. Chen, X. Huang, L. Wohlschlager, H. Renata, F. H. Arnold, *Nature* 2019, 565, 67–72; b) J. R. Griffin, C. I. Wendell, J. A. Garwin, C. M. White, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2017, 139, 13624–13627.
- [10] Y. Li, J.-S. Huang, Z.-Y. Zhou, C.-M. Che, X.-Z. You, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2002, 124, 13185–13193.
- [11] H. M. Mbuvi, L. K. Woo, *Organometallics* 2008, 27, 637–645.
- [12] C. Tortoreto, D. Rackl, H. M. Davies, *Org. Lett.* 2017, 19, 770–773.
- [13] a) P. R. Ortiz de Montellano, *Chem. Rev.* 2010, 110, 932–948; b) S. Chakrabarty, R. N. Austin, D. Deng, J. T. Groves, J. D. Lipscomb, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2007, 129, 3514–3515; c) J. C. Price, E. W. Barr, T. E. Glass, C. J. Krebs, J. Martin Bollinger, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2003, 125, 13008–13009; d) K. Chen, L. Que, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2001, 123, 6327–6337; e) A. Company, L. Glmez, M. Ggell, X. Ribas, J. M. Luis, L. Que, Jr., M. Costas, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2007, 129, 15766–15767.
- [14] a) E. T. Hennessy, T. A. Betley, *Science* 2013, 340, 591–595; b) B. Bagh, D. L. J. Broere, V. Sinha, P. F. Kuijpers, N. P. van Leest, B. de Bruin, S. Demeshko, M. A. Siegler, J. I. van der Vlugt, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2017, 139, 5117–5124.
- [15] a) M. M. Khusniyarov, T. Weyhermglger, E. Bill, K. Wieghardt, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2009, 131, 1208–1221; b) M. M. Khusniyarov, E. Bill, T. Weyhermglger, E. Bothe, K. Harms, J. Sundermeyer, K. Wieghardt, *Chem. Eur. J.* 2008, 14, 7608–7622.
- [16] a) V. M. Jimenez-Perez, M. Ibarra-Rodríguez, B. M. Muñoz-Flores, A. Glmez, R. Santillan, E. Hernández Fernández, S. BernHs, N. Waksman, R. Ramírez Duron, *J. Mol. Struct.* 2013, 1031, 168–174; b) M. M. Khusniyarov, K. Harms, O. Burghaus, J. Sundermeyer, B. Sarkar, W. Kaim, J. van Slageren, C. Duboc, J. Fiedler, *Dalton Trans.* 2008, 1355–1365.
- [17] a) F. Milocco, S. Demeshko, F. Meyer, E. Otten, *Dalton Trans.* 2018, 47, 8817–8823; b) R. Travieso-Puente, J. O. P. Broekman, M.-C. Chang, S. Demeshko, F. Meyer, E. Otten, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2016, 138, 5503–5506; c) W. D. Morris, P. T. Wolczanski, J. Sutter, K. Meyer, T. R. Cundari, E. B. Lobkovsky, *Inorg. Chem.* 2014, 53, 7467–7484; d) L. Zhang, L. Xiang, Y. Yu, L. Deng, *Inorg. Chem.* 2013, 52, 5906–5913; e) C. A. Nijhuis, E. Jellema, T. J. J. Sciarone, A. Meetsma, P. H. M. Budzelaar, B. Hessen, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* 2005, 2089–2099; f) A. Panda, M. Stender, R. J. Wright, M. M. Olmstead, P. Klavins, P. P. Power, *Inorg. Chem.* 2002, 41, 3909–3916; g) B. Vendemiati, G. Prini, A. Meetsma, B. Hessen, J. H. Teuben, O. Traverso, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* 2001, 707–711; h) J. R. Hagadorn, J. Arnold, *Inorg. Chem.* 1997, 36, 132–133.
- [18] T. Janes, J. M. Rawsonb, D. Song, *Dalton Trans.* 2013, 42, 10640–10648.
- [19] a) A. DeAngelis, R. Panish, J. M. Fox, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 2016, 49, 115–127, and references therein; b) D. F. Taber, M. J. Hennessy, J. P. Louey, *J. Org. Chem.* 1992, 57, 436–441; c) M. Lankelma, A. M. Olivares, B. de Bruin, *Chem. Eur. J.* 2019, 25, 5658–5663.
- [20] D. M. Seo, T. Afroz, J. L. Allen, P. D. Boyle, P. C. Trulove, H. C. De Long, W. A. Henderson, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 2014, 118, 25884–25889.
- [21] M. M. Díaz-Requejo, P. J. Pérez, *Chem. Rev.* 2008, 108, 3379–3394, and references therein.
- [22] M. Glmez-Gallego, M. A. Sierra, *Chem. Rev.* 2011, 111, 4857–4963.
- [23] G. A. Sulikowski, S. Lee, *Tetrahedron Lett.* 1999, 40, 8035–8038.
- [24] C. D.-T. Nielsen, J. Burss, *Chem. Sci.* 2019, 10, 348–353.